

Letter to Editor

Comment on: “Impact of Serum Albumin Levels on FDG Uptake in the Liver, Spleen, and Bone Marrow During Gastrointestinal Cancer Staging: A PET-CT Study”

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www.jeimp.com and digitalmkd.com**Dear Editor;**

I would like to thank you for presenting the valuable study titled “*Impact of Serum Albumin Levels on FDG Uptake in the Liver, Spleen, and Bone Marrow During Gastrointestinal Cancer Staging: A PET-CT Study*” in *The Journal of European Internal Medicine Professionals* (1). Your research is highly noteworthy for providing critical insights into the use of FDG PET-CT and shedding light on the evaluation of biomarkers in gastrointestinal system (GIS) cancers.

One of the strongest aspects of your study is the inclusion of a large cohort of 610 cancer patients, which enhances the generalizability of the findings. The detailed analyses of GIS cancer subtypes make a significant contribution to understanding the metabolic characteristics of these cancers. Evaluating the relationship between serum albumin levels and FDG PET-CT metabolic activity has the potential to provide clinically applicable results. Your findings, which demonstrate a significant relationship between albumin and liver FDG uptake, add novel insights to the existing literature.

Additionally, the exclusion of patients with metastatic liver disease and those undergoing treatment from your study sets it apart from prior research and underscores the contribution of your findings to the field (2). This approach enhances the emphasis on albumin as an independent risk factor, reinforcing its clinical importance. Furthermore, the meaningful and meticulously conducted statistical analyses lend credibility to your results.

The findings of this study raise curiosity about the relationship between albumin levels and the detection of metastases via PET-CT in patients with metastatic liver

malignancy. In addition to this study, serum albumin level is considered a powerful biomarker for disease prognosis and survival in various oncologic diseases, and its evaluation has also been proven beneficial in gastrointestinal cancers such as esophageal, colorectal cancer, and gastric cancer (3-5).

To further enhance your study, a prospective evaluation focusing on the rate of liver metastasis development in the analyzed patient cohort during follow-up could be included. This addition could strengthen your research by aiding in the evaluation of the correlation between albumin levels and FDG uptake, as well as their combined impact on the development of liver metastases and overall prognosis.

In conclusion, your study addresses a critical research area and presents valuable findings. I believe that your results will contribute to the advancement of both diagnostic and prognostic approaches in GIS cancers.

DECLERATIONS**Ethics committee approval:** Not necessary.**Financial disclosure:** None.**Conflicts of interest:** Author declares none.**Acknowledgments:** None.**AI:** Not applied**REFERENCES**

1. Cetinkaya E, Tuzcu ŞA. Impact of Serum Albumin Levels on FDG Uptake in the Liver, Spleen, and Bone Marrow During Gastrointestinal Cancer Staging: A PET-CT Study: FDG PET-CT Uptake in GIS Cancers. *J Eur Int Med Prof.* 2024;2(4):124-129.
2. Li WI, Ng K, Wong W, Ng K, Yong T, Kung B. Serum Albumin Alters [18F]FDG Activity in the Liver and Blood Pool. *World Journal of Nuclear Medicine.* 2024. doi: 10.1055/s-0044-1795100.
3. Wang CY, Hsieh MJ, Chiu YC, et al. Higher serum C-reactive protein concentration and hypoalbuminemia are poor prognostic indicators in patients with esophageal cancer undergoing radiotherapy. *Radiother*

- Oncol.* 2009;92(2):270-275. doi:10.1016/j.radonc.2009.01.002
4. Boonpipattanapong T, Chewatanakornkul S. Preoperative carcinoembryonic antigen and albumin in predicting survival in patients with colon and rectal carcinomas. *J Clin Gastroenterol.* 2006;40(7):592-595. doi:10.1097/00004836-200608000-00006
 5. Alici S, Kaya S, Izmirli M, et al. Analysis of survival factors in patients with advanced-stage gastric adenocarcinoma. *Med Sci Monit.* 2006;12(5):CR221-CR229.